

INTERVAL VALUED L-FUZZY IDEALS ON SEMINEARRINGS

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ABSTRACT. In this paper, we define a congruence relation on a seminearring and obtain the relationship with the existing congruence relations. In addition, we define an interval valued L-fuzzy ideal of a seminearring. Then we prove that if the level set is strong ideal of a seminearring S , then any L-fuzzy subset of a seminearring is a L-fuzzy ideal and the result is illustrated with the suitable example.

1. Introduction

A right seminearring is an algebraic structure which is a semigroup with respect to both the binary operations \cdot and $+$, satisfies right distributive law. Hoorn and Rootselaar[20] considered an ideal of a seminearring as a kernel of seminearring. Then Ahsan[2, 3] generalized this ideal definition and obtained results on ideals of seminearring. Koppula, Kedukodi and Kuncham[15] defined strong ideal of a seminearring and proved the classical isomorphism theorems. Fuzzy set theory was introduced by Zadeh[21]. Subsequently, various authors studied results on these fuzzy sets. L-fuzzy sets are introduced by Goguen[4], which are the combination of lattices and fuzzy sets. Jifan and Tiejun[9] defined fuzzy ideal in terms of t-norm and t-conorm and studied various properties. By using interval valued idempotent t-conorm and t-norm Li and Wang[17, 18] defined interval valued fuzzy ideals. Davvaz[1] studied interval valued fuzzy ideals on a distributive lattice. Results on L-fuzzy ideal of a ring are studied by Koc and Balkanay[12]. Then results on L-fuzzy left ideals and normal L-fuzzy ideals of semiring are studied by Jun, Neggers and Kim [10, 11]. The results on interval valued L-fuzzy ideals of a nearring using the concepts t-norm and t-conorm are studied by Jagadeesha, Kedukodi and Kuncham[7, 8].

In this paper, we define a congruence relation on a seminearring and obtain the relationship with the existing congruence relations. Later, we define interval valued L-fuzzy ideal of a seminearring. Then we prove that if the level set $\eta_{\bar{t}}$ is a strong ideal of S then the L -fuzzy subset of S is an interval valued L -fuzzy ideal of S .

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2. Preliminaries

Here, basic results and definitions are provided to obtain the results presented in the manuscript.

Definition 2.1. [20] Let S be a non-empty set. Then S is said to be a right seminearring with respect to $+$ and \cdot , if S is a semigroup with respect to both the operations $+$ and \cdot , and satisfies the following conditions.

- (1) $(a_2 + a_3)a_1 = a_2a_1 + a_3a_1, \forall a_1, a_2, a_3 \in S$.
- (2) $0 + a_1 = a_1 + 0 = a_1, \forall a_1 \in S$.
- (3) For all $a_1 \in S, 0a_1 = 0$.

Definition 2.2. Let T be a nonempty subset of S . Then, for $a_1, a_2 \in S, a_1 \equiv_T a_2$ if and only if there exist $i_1, i_2 \in T$ such that $i_1 + a_1 = i_2 + a_2$.

Through out this paper, S is considered as a right seminearring.

Definition 2.3. [15] A non-empty subset A of S is a strong ideal of S , if the following mentioned conditions hold.

- (1) $a_1 + a_2 \in A$, for all $a_1, a_2 \in A$.
- (2) $s_1 + A \subseteq A + s_1, \forall s_1 \in S$.
- (3) For $s_1, s_2 \in S$, if $s_1 \equiv_A s_2$ then $s_1 \in A + s_2$.
- (4) $s_1(A + s_2) \subseteq A + s_1s_2$ for all $s_1, s_2 \in S$.
- (5) $As_1 \subseteq A$ for all $s_1 \in S$.

Definition 2.4. [15] Let A be any non-empty subset of S . For $s_1, s_2 \in S, s_1 \equiv_A s_2$ implies there exist $a_1, a_2 \in A$ such that $s_1 + a_1 = s_2 + a_2$.

Definition 2.5. An equivalence relation ρ on S is said to be a congruence relation on S , if $a_1 \rho a_2$ and $a_3 \rho a_4$

- (1) Then $(a_1 + a_3) \rho (a_2 + a_4)$
- (2) Then $(a_1a_3) \rho (a_2a_4)$.

Definition 2.6. [15] Let $\phi : S \rightarrow R$ be a seminearring homomorphism. Then

$$\ker \phi = \{s \in S \mid \phi(s) = \phi(0)\}.$$

Definition 2.7. [15] Let S and R be seminearrings. Then a homomorphism $\phi : S \rightarrow R$ is said to be a strong homomorphism if $\phi(x) = \phi(y)$ then $x \in \ker \phi + y$.

Theorem 2.8. [15] The following statements hold.

1. The projection map $\pi : S \rightarrow S/P$ is an onto seminearring strong homomorphism.
2. If $\phi : S \rightarrow R$ is an onto seminearring strong homomorphism then $\ker \phi$ is a strong ideal of S and $S/\ker \phi \cong R$.

Definition 2.9. [16] Let η be a fuzzy subset of seminearring S and $\tau_1, \tau_2 \in [0, 1]$ are thresholds of S such that $\tau_1 < \tau_2$. Then η is called a fuzzy ideal of a seminearring S with τ_1 and τ_2 , if the below mentioned conditions are satisfied.

- (1) $\tau_1 \vee \eta(p + q) \geq \tau_2 \wedge \eta(p) \wedge \eta(q)$
- (2) If $x + a = y + b$ then $\tau_1 \vee \eta(a) \geq \tau_2 \wedge \eta(y + b) \wedge \eta(x), a, b, x, y \in S$.

- (3) $\tau_1 \vee \eta(p + q + r) \geq \tau_2 \wedge \eta(q) \wedge \eta(q + p + r)$
- (4) $\tau_1 \vee \eta(p(q + r) + t) \geq \tau_2 \wedge \eta(q) \wedge \eta(pr + t)$
- (5) $\tau_1 \vee \eta(pq) \geq \tau_2 \wedge \eta(p)$, for all $p, q, r, t \in S$.

In the above definition, τ_2 and τ_1 are known as upper and lower thresholds of S respectively.

If $\tau_2 = 1$ and $\tau_1 = 0$, then η is an ordinary fuzzy ideal of S .

In this paper, we consider $\langle L, \wedge_L, \vee_L \rangle$ is a complete bounded lattice with the partial ordering relation \leq_L .

Definition 2.10. [6] Let L be a lattice. A t-norm $T : L \times L \rightarrow L$ is a function such that if the following conditions are satisfied. For all $l_1, l_2, l_3 \in L$,

- (1) $T(l_1, T(l_2, l_3)) = T(T(l_1, l_2), l_3)$ (Associativity)
- (2) $T(l_1, l_2) = T(l_2, l_1)$ (Commutativity)
- (3) If $l_2 \leq_L l_3$ then $T(l_1, l_2) \leq_L T(l_1, l_3)$ (Monotonicity)
- (4) $T(l_1, M) = l_1$, where M is the greatest element of L (Boundary condition).

In the following, T denotes a t-norm on L .

If $T(l_1, l_1) = l_1, \forall l_1 \in L$ then T is said to be idempotent t-norm.

Definition 2.11. [22] A t-conorm $C : L \times L \rightarrow L$ is a function such that if the following mentioned conditions are satisfied. For all $l_1, l_2, l_3 \in L$,

- (1) $C(l_1, C(l_2, l_3)) = C(C(l_1, l_2), l_3)$ (Associativity)
- (2) $C(l_1, l_2) = C(l_2, l_1)$ (Commutativity)
- (3) If $l_2 \leq_L l_3$ then $C(l_1, l_2) \leq_L C(l_1, l_3)$ (Monotonicity)
- (4) $C(l_1, m) = l_1$, where m is the least element of L (Boundary condition).

In the following, C denotes a t-conorm on L .

Remark 2.12. $T(l_1, l_2) \leq_L l_1 \wedge_L l_2 \leq_L l_1 \vee_L l_2 \leq_L C(l_1, l_2)$.

The set $D(L) = \{[x, y] \mid x, y \in L\}$. Let $I_1 = [x_1, y_1]$ and $I_2 = [x_2, y_2]$ be two elements of $D(L)$. Then $I_1 \leq I_2 \Leftrightarrow x_1 \leq_L x_2$ and $y_1 \leq_L y_2$.

Definition 2.13. Let A be any non-empty subset of X . A mapping $\eta : A \rightarrow L$ is called a L-fuzzy subset of A . Now, consider $\underline{\eta}, \bar{\eta}$ are any two L-fuzzy subsets of A such that $\underline{\eta}(a) \leq \bar{\eta}(a), \forall a \in A$.

Define a mapping $\hat{\eta} : A \rightarrow D(L)$ as $\hat{\eta} = [\underline{\eta}(a), \bar{\eta}(a)], \forall a \in A$. Then $\hat{\eta}$ is called an interval valued L-fuzzy subset of A .

For more results on nearrings, semirings and seminearrings, we refer Pilz[19], Golan[5], Koppula, Kedukodi and Kuncham[13, 14].

3. Congruence relations on seminearring

In the present section, we provide a congruence relation and obtained the relationship with the existing congruence relations. Then we define interval valued L-fuzzy ideal using t-norm and t-conorm and proved the related results.

Definition 3.1. Let A be a strong ideal of seminearring S and $s_1, s_2 \in S$. Then $s_1 \stackrel{A}{=} s_2$ if and only if there exist $a_1, a_2, a_3, a_4 \in A$ such that $a_1 + s_1 + a_2 = a_3 + s_2 + a_4$.

Proposition 3.2. If A is a strong ideal of seminearring S and $s_1, s_2 \in S$ then $s_1 \equiv_A s_2$ implies $s_1 \stackrel{A}{=} s_2$.

Proof. Suppose $s_1 \equiv_A s_2$. Then there exist $a_1, a_2 \in A$ such that $s_1 + a_1 = s_2 + a_2$. As A is a strong ideal of S , there exist $a'_1, a'_2 \in A$ such that $a'_1 + s_1 = a'_2 + s_2$. This implies $s_1 \stackrel{A}{=} s_2$. \square

Proposition 3.3. If A is a strong ideal of seminearring S then $\stackrel{A}{=}$ is a congruence relation on S .

Proof. Clearly, $\stackrel{A}{=}$ is reflexive and symmetric. Now, consider $x \stackrel{A}{=} y$ and $y \stackrel{A}{=} z$. Then there exist $i_1, i_2, i_3, i_4, i_5, i_6, i_7, i_8 \in A$ such that $i_1 + x + i_2 = i_3 + y + i_4$ and $i_5 + y + i_6 = i_7 + z + i_8$.

Now, $i_5 + (i_1 + x + i_2) + i_6 = i_5 + (i_3 + y + i_4) + i_6 = i_5 + i_3 + (y + i_4) + i_6$

$\implies (i_5 + i_1) + x + (i_2 + i_6) = i_5 + i_3 + (i'_4 + y) + i_6$, for some $i'_4 \in A$.

$\implies i'_1 + x + i'_2 = (i_5 + i'_5) + y + i_6$

$(i_5 + i_1 = i'_1 \in A, i_2 + i_6 = i'_2 \in A \quad \text{and} \quad i_3 + i'_4 = i'_5 \in A)$

$\implies i'_1 + x + i'_2 = (i'_6 + i_5) + y + i_6$, for some $i'_6 \in A$.

$\implies i'_1 + x + i'_2 = i'_6 + (i_5 + y + i_6)$

$\implies i'_1 + x + i'_2 = i'_6 + (i_7 + z + i_8)$

$\implies i'_1 + x + i'_2 = i'_7 + z + i_8$ ($i'_6 + i_7 = i'_7 \in A$)

This implies $x \stackrel{A}{=} z$.

Thus, the relation $\stackrel{A}{=}$ is an equivalence relation on S .

Now, we show that the relation $\stackrel{A}{=}$ is congruence relation on S .

Suppose $x \stackrel{A}{=} y$ and $x' \stackrel{A}{=} y'$.

Then there exist $i_1, i_2, i_3, i_4, i_5, i_6, i_7, i_8 \in A$ such that $i_1 + x + i_2 = i_3 + y + i_4$ and $i_5 + x' + i_6 = i_7 + y' + i_8$.

Now, we have $(i_1 + x + i_2) + (i_5 + x' + i_6) = (i_3 + y + i_4) + (i_7 + y' + i_8)$

$\implies i_1 + (x + i_2) + (i_5 + x' + i_6) = i_3 + (y + i_4) + (i_7 + y' + i_8)$

$\implies i_1 + (x + i_2) + (i_5 + x' + i_6) = i_3 + (y + i_4) + (i_7 + y' + i_8)$

$\implies i_1 + (i'_2 + x) + (i_5 + x' + i_6) = i_3 + (i'_4 + y) + (i_7 + y' + i_8)$, for some $i'_2, i'_4 \in A$.

$\implies i_1 + i'_2 + (x + i_5) + x' + i_6 = i_3 + i'_4 + (y + i_7) + y' + i_8$

$\implies i_1 + i'_2 + (i'_5 + x) + x' + i_6 = i_3 + i'_4 + (i'_7 + y) + y' + i_8$ for some $i'_5, i'_7 \in A$.

$\implies i_9 + x + x' + i_6 = i_{10} + y + y' + i_8$

$(i_1 + i'_2 + i'_5 = i_9 \in A, i_3 + i'_4 + i'_7 = i_{10} \in A)$

This implies $x + x' \stackrel{A}{=} y + y'$.

Now, consider $(i_1 + x + i_2)(i_5 + x' + i_6) = (i_3 + y + i_4)(i_7 + y' + i_8)$

$\implies (i_1 + x)(i_5 + x' + i_6) + i_2(i_5 + x' + i_6) = (i_3 + y)(i_7 + y' + i_8) + i_4(i_7 + y' + i_8)$

$\implies i_1(i_5 + x' + i_6) + x(i_5 + (x' + i_6)) + i'_2 = i_3(i_7 + y' + i_8) + y(i_7 + (y' + i_8)) + i''_4$

$[i_2(i_5 + x' + i_6) = i''_2 \in A \text{ and } i_4(i_7 + y' + i_8) = i''_4 \in A]$

As A is a strong ideal of S , we get $i_1'' + (i_5'' + x(x' + i_6)) + i_2'' = i_3'' + (i_7'' + y(y' + i_8)) + i_4''$, for some $i_5'', i_7'' \in A$ [$i_1(i_5' + x' + i_6) = i_1'' \in A$ and $i_3(i_7' + y' + i_8) = i_3'' \in A$].
 $\Rightarrow i_1'' + i_5'' + x(i_6' + x') + i_2'' = i_3'' + i_7'' + y(i_8' + y') + i_4''$ for some $i_6', i_8' \in A$.
 $\Rightarrow i_1'' + i_5'' + i_6'' + xx' + i_2'' = i_3'' + i_7'' + i_8'' + yy' + i_4''$ for some $i_6'', i_8'' \in A$.
 $\Rightarrow i_9'' + xx' + i_2'' = i_{10}'' + yy' + i_4''$ [$i_1'' + i_5'' + i_6'' = i_9'' \in A$ and $i_3'' + i_7'' + i_8'' = i_{10}'' \in A$]
 This implies $xx' \stackrel{A}{=} yy'$. Thus, the relation $\stackrel{A}{=}$ is a congruence relation on S . \square

Proposition 3.4. If A is a strong ideal of seminearring S , and $x, y \in S$, then $x \stackrel{A}{=} y$ if and only if $x \equiv_A y$.

Proof. First, we assume that $x \stackrel{A}{=} y$. This implies there exist $i_1, i_2, i_3, i_4 \in A$ such that $i_1 + (x + i_2) = i_3 + (y + i_4)$.
 Then there exist $i_2', i_4' \in A$ such that $i_1 + (i_2' + x) = i_3 + (i_4' + y)$.
 This implies $(i_1 + i_2') + x = (i_3 + i_4') + y$.
 Then $i_1' + x = i_3' + y$
 $(i_1 + i_2' = i_1' \in A$ and $i_3 + i_4' = i_3' \in A)$.
 This implies $x \equiv_A y$.

Conversely, $x \equiv_A y$ implies there exist $a_1, a_2 \in A$ such that $a_1 + x = a_2 + y$.
 This also can be written as $a_1 + x + 0 = a_2 + y + 0$. This implies $x \stackrel{A}{=} y$. \square

Proposition 3.5. If $\varphi : S \rightarrow S'$ is a seminearring homomorphism and η is a fuzzy ideal of S' then $\varphi^{-1}(\eta)$ is a fuzzy ideal of S .

Proof. Let $s_1, s_2 \in S$. Then consider $\tau_1 \vee \varphi^{-1}(\eta)(s_1 + s_2) = \tau_1 \vee \eta(\varphi(s_1 + s_2))$
 $= \tau_1 \vee \eta(\varphi(s_1) + \varphi(s_2))$
 $\geq \tau_2 \wedge \eta(\varphi(s_1)) \wedge \eta(\varphi(s_2))$ (Because η is a fuzzy ideal of S' .)
 $= \tau_2 \wedge \varphi^{-1}(\eta)(s_1) \wedge \varphi^{-1}(\eta)(s_2)$.
 Let $x, y, s_1, s_2 \in S$ be such that $x + s_1 = y + s_2$.
 Then $\varphi(x + s_1) = \varphi(y + s_2)$. As φ is a homomorphism, then we have $\varphi(x) + \varphi(s_1) = \varphi(y) + \varphi(s_2)$.
 Now, $\tau_1 \vee \varphi^{-1}(\eta)(s_1) = \tau_1 \vee \eta(\varphi(s_1))$
 $\geq \tau_2 \wedge \eta(\varphi(y) + \varphi(s_2)) \wedge \eta(\varphi(x))$ (Because η is a fuzzy ideal of S' .)
 $= \tau_2 \wedge \eta(\varphi(y + s_2)) \wedge \eta(\varphi(x))$
 $= \tau_2 \wedge \varphi^{-1}(\eta)(y + s_2) \wedge \varphi^{-1}(\eta)(x)$.
 Let $a, b, c \in S$ be such that $\tau_1 \vee \varphi^{-1}(\eta)(a + b + c) = \tau_1 \vee \eta(\varphi(a + b + c))$
 $= \tau_1 \vee \eta(\varphi(a) + \varphi(b) + \varphi(c))$
 $\geq \tau_2 \wedge \eta(\varphi(b)) \wedge \eta(\varphi(b) + \varphi(a) + \varphi(c))$
 $= \tau_2 \wedge \eta(\varphi(b)) \wedge \eta(\varphi(b + a + c))$
 $= \tau_2 \wedge \varphi^{-1}(\eta)(b) \wedge \varphi^{-1}(\eta)(b + a + c)$.
 Now, take $a, b, c, t \in S$ such that $\tau_1 \vee \varphi^{-1}(\eta)(a(b + c) + t) = \tau_1 \vee \eta(\varphi(a(b + c) + t))$
 $= \tau_1 \vee \eta(\varphi(a(b + c)) + \varphi(t)) = \tau_1 \vee \eta(\varphi(a)\varphi(b + c) + \varphi(t))$
 $= \tau_1 \vee \eta(\varphi(a)(\varphi(b) + \varphi(c)) + \varphi(t))$
 $\geq \tau_2 \wedge \eta(\varphi(b)) \wedge \eta(\varphi(a)\varphi(c) + \varphi(t))$
 $= \tau_2 \wedge \eta(\varphi(b)) \wedge \eta(\varphi(ac) + \varphi(t))$
 $= \tau_2 \wedge \eta(\varphi(b)) \wedge \eta(\varphi(ac + t))$
 $= \tau_2 \wedge \varphi^{-1}(\eta)(b) \wedge \varphi^{-1}(\eta)(ac + t)$.

Now, take $a, b \in S$ such that $\tau_1 \vee \varphi^{-1}(\eta)(ab) = \tau_1 \vee \eta(\varphi(ab))$
 $\geq \tau_2 \wedge \eta(\varphi(a)) = \tau_2 \wedge \varphi^{-1}(\eta)(a)$.
 Thus $\varphi^{-1}(\eta)$ is a fuzzy ideal of S . \square

Definition 3.6. Let $(S, +, \cdot)$ be a seminearring and T_{IL}, C_{IL} be interval valued t-norm and t-conorm on $D(L)$. Let $\hat{\tau}_1, \hat{\tau}_2 \in D(L)$ be the thresholds such that $\hat{\tau}_1 < \hat{\tau}_2$. An interval valued L -fuzzy subset $\hat{\eta}$ on S is said to be an interval valued L -fuzzy ideal with $\hat{\tau}_1, \hat{\tau}_2$ such that if the below mentioned conditions hold. For all $s_1, s_2, s_3, t \in S$,

- (1) $C_{IL}(\hat{\tau}_1, \hat{\eta}(s_1 + s_2)) \geq T_{IL}(\hat{\tau}_2, T_{IL}(C_{IL}(\hat{\tau}_1, \hat{\eta}(s_1)), C_{IL}(\hat{\tau}_1, \hat{\eta}(s_2))))$
- (2) If $x_1 + a = x_2 + b$ then
 $C_{IL}(\hat{\tau}_1, \hat{\eta}(a)) \geq T_{IL}(\hat{\tau}_2, T_{IL}(C_{IL}(\hat{\tau}_1, \hat{\eta}(x_2 + b)), C_{IL}(\hat{\tau}_1, \hat{\eta}(x_1))))$,
 $a, b, x_1, x_2 \in S$.
- (3) $C_{IL}(\hat{\tau}_1, \hat{\eta}(s_1 + s_2 + s_3)) \geq T_{IL}(\hat{\tau}_2, T_{IL}(C_{IL}(\hat{\tau}_1, \hat{\eta}(s_2)), C_{IL}(\hat{\tau}_1, \hat{\eta}(s_2 + s_1 + s_3))))$
- (4) $C_{IL}(\hat{\tau}_1, \hat{\eta}(s_1(s_2 + s_3) + t)) \geq T_{IL}(\hat{\tau}_2, T_{IL}(C_{IL}(\hat{\tau}_1, \hat{\eta}(s_2)), C_{IL}(\hat{\tau}_1, \hat{\eta}(s_1 s_3 + t))))$
- (5) $C_{IL}(\hat{\tau}_1, \hat{\eta}(s_1 s_2)) \geq T_{IL}(\hat{\tau}_2, C_{IL}(\hat{\tau}_1, \hat{\eta}(s_1)))$.

Proposition 3.7. If $\hat{\eta}$ is an interval valued L -fuzzy subset of S and the level set $\eta_{\hat{t}}, \forall \hat{t} \in (\hat{\tau}_1, \hat{\tau}_2]$ is a strong ideal of S then $\hat{\eta}$ is an interval valued L -fuzzy ideal of S .

Proof. First, we will show that

$C_{IL}(\hat{\tau}_1, \hat{\eta}(x+y)) \geq T_{IL}(\hat{\tau}_2, T_{IL}(C_{IL}(\hat{\tau}_1, \hat{\eta}(x)), C_{IL}(\hat{\tau}_1, \hat{\eta}(y))))$, $\forall x, y \in S$. Suppose, we assume that $C_{IL}(\hat{\tau}_1, \hat{\eta}(x+y)) \leq T_{IL}(\hat{\tau}_2, T_{IL}(C_{IL}(\hat{\tau}_1, \hat{\eta}(x)), C_{IL}(\hat{\tau}_1, \hat{\eta}(y))))$, for some x and y .

Let $\hat{t} = T_{IL}(\hat{\tau}_2, T_{IL}(C_{IL}(\hat{\tau}_1, \hat{\eta}(x)), C_{IL}(\hat{\tau}_1, \hat{\eta}(y))))$.

Then $\hat{t} \leq \hat{\tau}_2 \wedge T_{IL}(C_{IL}(\hat{\tau}_1, \hat{\eta}(x)), C_{IL}(\hat{\tau}_1, \hat{\eta}(y)))$.

$\leq \hat{\tau}_2 \wedge C_{IL}(\hat{\tau}_1, \hat{\eta}(x)) \wedge C_{IL}(\hat{\tau}_1, \hat{\eta}(y))$

$\Rightarrow \hat{t} \leq \hat{\tau}_2$, $\hat{t} \leq C_{IL}(\hat{\tau}_1, \hat{\eta}(x))$ and $\hat{t} \leq C_{IL}(\hat{\tau}_1, \hat{\eta}(y))$.

$\Rightarrow x \in \hat{\eta}_{\hat{t}}, y \in \hat{\eta}_{\hat{t}}$.

As $C_{IL}(\hat{\tau}_1, \hat{\eta}(x+y)) < \hat{t}$, we get $x+y \notin \hat{\eta}_{\hat{t}}$.

Now, $x \in \hat{\eta}_{\hat{t}}, y \in \hat{\eta}_{\hat{t}}$ and $x+y \notin \hat{\eta}_{\hat{t}}$. This is a contradiction to $\hat{\eta}_{\hat{t}}$ is a strong ideal of S .

Let $x, a, y, b \in S$ such that $x+a = y+b$.

Then we show that $C_{IL}(\hat{\tau}_1, \hat{\eta}(a)) \geq T_{IL}(\hat{\tau}_2, T_{IL}(C_{IL}(\hat{\tau}_1, \hat{\eta}(y+b)), C_{IL}(\hat{\tau}_1, \hat{\eta}(x))))$.

Suppose $C_{IL}(\hat{\tau}_1, \hat{\eta}(a)) < T_{IL}(\hat{\tau}_2, T_{IL}(C_{IL}(\hat{\tau}_1, \hat{\eta}(y+b)), C_{IL}(\hat{\tau}_1, \hat{\eta}(x))))$,

for some $x, y, a, b \in S$. Let $\hat{t} \in (\hat{\tau}_1, \hat{\tau}_2]$ such that

$C_{IL}(\hat{\tau}_1, \hat{\eta}(a)) < \hat{t} < T_{IL}(\hat{\tau}_2, T_{IL}(C_{IL}(\hat{\tau}_1, \hat{\eta}(y+b)), C_{IL}(\hat{\tau}_1, \hat{\eta}(x))))$. This implies

$C_{IL}(\hat{\tau}_1, \hat{\eta}(a)) < \hat{t}$ and $\hat{t} < T_{IL}(\hat{\tau}_2, T_{IL}(C_{IL}(\hat{\tau}_1, \hat{\eta}(y+b)), C_{IL}(\hat{\tau}_1, \hat{\eta}(x)))) \leq \hat{\tau}_2 \wedge$

$T_{IL}(C_{IL}(\hat{\tau}_1, \hat{\eta}(y+b)), C_{IL}(\hat{\tau}_1, \hat{\eta}(x)))$

$\Rightarrow a \notin \hat{\eta}_{\hat{t}}$ and $\hat{t} \leq \hat{\tau}_2 \wedge C_{IL}(\hat{\tau}_1, \hat{\eta}(x)) \wedge C_{IL}(\hat{\tau}_1, \hat{\eta}(y+b))$

$\Rightarrow \hat{t} \leq \hat{\tau}_2$, $\hat{t} \leq C_{IL}(\hat{\tau}_1, \hat{\eta}(x))$ and $\hat{t} \leq (C_{IL}(\hat{\tau}_1, \hat{\eta}(y+b)))$ and $a \notin \hat{\eta}_{\hat{t}}$.

This implies $x \in \hat{\eta}_{\hat{t}}$ and $y+b \in \hat{\eta}_{\hat{t}}$ and $a \notin \hat{\eta}_{\hat{t}}$.

As $x \in \hat{\eta}_{\hat{t}}, y+b \in \hat{\eta}_{\hat{t}}$ and $x+a = y+b$, we get $a \equiv_{\hat{\eta}_{\hat{t}}} 0$. This implies $a \in \hat{\eta}_{\hat{t}}$, (Because $\hat{\eta}_{\hat{t}}$ is a strong ideal of S), which is a contradiction.

Now, we have to show that

$$C_{IL}(\hat{\tau}_1, \hat{\eta}(s_1 + s_2 + r)) \geq T_{IL}(\hat{\tau}_2, T_{IL}(C_{IL}(\hat{\tau}_1, \hat{\eta}(s_2)), C_{IL}(\hat{\tau}_1, \hat{\eta}(s_2 + s_1 + r))))),$$

$\forall s_1, s_2, r \in S$. Suppose there exist $s_1, s_2, r \in S$ such that

$$C_{IL}(\hat{\tau}_1, \hat{\eta}(s_1 + s_2 + r)) < T_{IL}(\hat{\tau}_2, T_{IL}(C_{IL}(\hat{\tau}_1, \hat{\eta}(s_2)), C_{IL}(\hat{\tau}_1, \hat{\eta}(s_2 + s_1 + r)))).$$

Let $\hat{t} \in (\hat{\tau}_1, \hat{\tau}_2]$ such that

$$C_{IL}(\hat{\tau}_1, \hat{\eta}(s_1 + s_2 + r)) < \hat{t} < T_{IL}(\hat{\tau}_2, T_{IL}(C_{IL}(\hat{\tau}_1, \hat{\eta}(s_2)), C_{IL}(\hat{\tau}_1, \hat{\eta}(s_2 + s_1 + r)))).$$

Then $C_{IL}(\hat{\tau}_1, \hat{\eta}(s_1 + s_2 + r)) < \hat{t}$ and $\hat{t} \leq \hat{\tau}_2 \wedge T_{IL}(C_{IL}(\hat{\tau}_1, \hat{\eta}(s_2)), C_{IL}(\hat{\tau}_1, \hat{\eta}(s_2 + s_1 + r)))$.

$$\Rightarrow s_1 + s_2 + r \notin \hat{\eta}_{\hat{t}} \text{ and } \hat{t} \leq \hat{\tau}_2 \wedge C_{IL}(\hat{\tau}_1, \hat{\eta}(s_2)) \wedge C_{IL}(\hat{\tau}_1, \hat{\eta}(s_2 + s_1 + r)).$$

This implies $s_2 \in \hat{\eta}_{\hat{t}}$, $s_2 + s_1 + r \in \hat{\eta}_{\hat{t}}$ and $s_1 + s_2 + r \notin \hat{\eta}_{\hat{t}}$.

As $\hat{\eta}_{\hat{t}}$ is a strong ideal of S , $s_2 \in \hat{\eta}_{\hat{t}}$ and $s_2 + s_1 + r \in \hat{\eta}_{\hat{t}}$ implies $s_1 + r \in \hat{\eta}_{\hat{t}}$. Because $s_2 \in \hat{\eta}_{\hat{t}}$, there exists $q_1 \in \hat{\eta}_{\hat{t}}$ such that $(s_1 + s_2) + r = (q_1 + s_1) + r \in \hat{\eta}_{\hat{t}}$, which is a contradiction to $s_1 + s_2 + r \notin \hat{\eta}_{\hat{t}}$.

Now, suppose there exist $s_1, s_2, r, t \in S$ such that $C_{IL}(\hat{\tau}_1, \hat{\eta}(s_1(s_2 + r) + t)) < T_{IL}(\hat{\tau}_2, T_{IL}(C_{IL}(\hat{\tau}_1, \hat{\eta}(s_2)), C_{IL}(\hat{\tau}_1, \hat{\eta}(s_1r + t))))$. Let $\hat{t} \in (\hat{\tau}_1, \hat{\tau}_2]$ such that

$$C_{IL}(\hat{\tau}_1, \hat{\eta}(s_1(s_2 + r) + t)) < \hat{t} < T_{IL}(\hat{\tau}_2, T_{IL}(C_{IL}(\hat{\tau}_1, \hat{\eta}(s_2)), C_{IL}(\hat{\tau}_1, \hat{\eta}(s_1r + t)))).$$

This implies $C_{IL}(\hat{\tau}_1, \hat{\eta}(s_1(s_2 + r) + t)) < \hat{t}$ and

$$\hat{t} \leq \hat{\tau}_2 \wedge T_{IL}(C_{IL}(\hat{\tau}_1, \hat{\eta}(s_2)), C_{IL}(\hat{\tau}_1, \hat{\eta}(s_1r + t))).$$

This gives $t \leq \hat{\tau}_2 \wedge C_{IL}(\hat{\tau}_1, \hat{\eta}(s_2)) \wedge C_{IL}(\hat{\tau}_1, \hat{\eta}(s_1r + t))$ and $s_1(s_2 + r) + t \in \hat{\eta}_{\hat{t}}$.

This implies $s_2 \in \hat{\eta}_{\hat{t}}$, $s_1r + t \in \hat{\eta}_{\hat{t}}$ and $s_1(s_2 + r) + t \notin \hat{\eta}_{\hat{t}}$.

As $\hat{\eta}_{\hat{t}}$ is a strong ideal of S and $s_2 \in \hat{\eta}_{\hat{t}}$ then $s_1(s_2 + r) + t = q_1 + s_1r + t \in \hat{\eta}_{\hat{t}}$ for some $q_1 \in \hat{\eta}_{\hat{t}}$.

This implies $s_1(s_2 + r) + t \in \hat{\eta}_{\hat{t}}$.

This is a contradiction.

$$\text{Hence } C_{IL}(\hat{\tau}_1, \hat{\eta}(s_1(s_2 + r) + t)) \geq T_{IL}(\hat{\tau}_2, T_{IL}(C_{IL}(\hat{\tau}_1, \hat{\eta}(s_2)), C_{IL}(\hat{\tau}_1, \hat{\eta}(s_1r + t)))).$$

Now, we assume that $C_{IL}(\hat{\tau}_1, \hat{\eta}(s_1s_2)) < T_{IL}(\hat{\tau}_2, C_{IL}(\hat{\tau}_1, \hat{\eta}(s_1)))$, for some $s_1, s_2 \in S$. Then there exists $\hat{t} \in (\hat{\tau}_1, \hat{\tau}_2]$ such that

$$C_{IL}(\hat{\tau}_1, \hat{\eta}(s_1s_2)) < \hat{t} < T_{IL}(\hat{\tau}_2, C_{IL}(\hat{\tau}_1, \hat{\eta}(s_1))).$$

This implies $\hat{t} \leq \hat{\tau}_2 \wedge C_{IL}(\hat{\tau}_1, \hat{\eta}(s_1))$ and $s_1s_2 \notin \hat{\eta}_{\hat{t}}$. This gives $s_1 \in \hat{\eta}_{\hat{t}}$ and $s_1s_2 \notin \hat{\eta}_{\hat{t}}$. This is a contradiction. Hence $\hat{\eta}$ is an interval valued L -fuzzy ideal of S . \square

The following mentioned example shows that, if $\hat{\eta}$ is an interval valued L -fuzzy ideal of S then $\hat{\eta}_{\hat{t}}$, $\hat{t} \in (\hat{\tau}_1, \hat{\tau}_2]$ need not be a strong ideal of S .

Example 3.8. Let $S = \{0, p, q, r\}$ be a set with respect to $+$ and \cdot defined as follows.

+	0	p	q	r
0	0	p	q	r
p	p	p	q	r
q	q	r	q	r
r	r	r	q	r

.	0	p	q	r
0	0	0	0	0
p	0	p	0	0
q	q	q	q	q
r	q	r	q	q

Then $(S, +, \cdot)$ is a right seminearring. Now, we consider the lattice L as shown in the following figure.

Define $\hat{\eta} : S \rightarrow D(L)$ as shown in the below.

$$\hat{\eta}(s) = \begin{cases} [t, M] & \text{if } s = 0 \\ [r, s] & \text{if } s = p \\ [p, s] & \text{if } s \in \{q, r\}. \end{cases}$$

$$C_{fL}(s_1, s_2) = s_1 \vee s_2$$

$$C_{sL}(s_1, s_2) = \begin{cases} s_1 & \text{if } s_2 = m \\ s_2 & \text{if } s_1 = m \\ M & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

Let $\hat{\tau}_1 = [m, q]$ and $\hat{\tau}_2 = [r, s]$.

Then $C_{IL}(\hat{\alpha}, \hat{\eta}(0)) = [C_{fL}(m, r), C_{sL}(q, s)] = [t, M]$

Similarly, $T_{IL}(\hat{\alpha}, \hat{\eta}(0)) = [T_{fL}(m, r), T_{sL}(q, s)]$.

$C_{IL}(\hat{\alpha}, \hat{\eta}(a)) = [r, M]$

$C_{IL}(\hat{\alpha}, \hat{\eta}(b)) = C_I(\hat{\alpha}, \hat{\eta}(c)) = [p, M]$.

Then $\hat{\eta}$ is an interval valued L-fuzzy ideal of S .

Let $\hat{t} = [r, s]$. Then $\alpha < \hat{t} \leq \beta$.

Then $\eta_{\hat{t}} = \{0, p\}$ is not a strong ideal of S .

Because $q + \{0, p\} = \{q, r\} \not\subseteq \{0, p\} + q = q$.

F1: For $a, b \in S$, if $C_{IL}(\hat{\tau}_1, \hat{\eta}(a)) \geq T_{IL}(\hat{\tau}_2, T_{IL}(C_{IL}(\hat{\tau}_1, \hat{\eta}(b)), \hat{t}))$, then we assume that $a \in \eta_{\hat{t}} + b, \forall \hat{t} \in (\hat{\tau}_1, \hat{\tau}_2]$.

Proposition 3.9. If $\hat{\eta}$ is an interval L-fuzzy ideal of a seminearring S , T_{IL} is an idempotent interval valued t-norm on $D(L)$ and satisfies condition F1, then $\eta_{\hat{t}}, \forall \hat{t} \in (\hat{\tau}_1, \hat{\tau}_2]$ is a strong ideal of seminearring S .

Proof. Let $s_1, s_2 \in \eta_{\hat{t}}$. Then $C_{IL}(\hat{\tau}_1, \hat{\eta}(s_1)) \geq \hat{t}$ and $C_{IL}(\hat{\tau}_1, \hat{\eta}(s_2)) \geq \hat{t}$.

As $\hat{\eta}$ is an interval L-fuzzy ideal of a seminearring S , we have

$C_{IL}(\hat{\tau}_1, \hat{\eta}(s_1 + s_2)) \geq T_{IL}(\hat{\tau}_2, T_{IL}(C_{IL}(\hat{\tau}_1, \hat{\eta}(s_1)), C_{IL}(\hat{\tau}_1, \hat{\eta}(s_2))))$.

This implies $C_{IL}(\hat{\tau}_1, \hat{\eta}(s_1 + s_2)) \geq T_{IL}(\hat{\tau}_2, T_{IL}(\hat{t}, (C_{IL}(\hat{\tau}_1, \hat{\eta}(s_2))))$
 $\Rightarrow C_{IL}(\hat{\tau}_1, \hat{\eta}(s_1 + s_2)) \geq T_{IL}(\hat{\tau}_2, T_{IL}(\hat{t}, \hat{t}))$
 $\Rightarrow C_{IL}(\hat{\tau}_1, \hat{\eta}(s_1 + s_2)) \geq T_{IL}(\hat{\tau}_2, \hat{t}) \geq T_{IL}(\hat{t}, \hat{t}) = \hat{t}$.

This implies $s_1 + s_2 \in \eta_{\hat{t}}$.

Now, take $s \in S$ such that $a \in s + \eta_{\hat{t}}$. Then there exists $i_1 \in \eta_{\hat{t}}$ such that $a = s + i_1$.

As $\hat{\eta}$ is an interval L-fuzzy ideal of a seminearring S , we have $C_{IL}(\hat{\tau}_1, \hat{\eta}(a)) = C_{IL}(\hat{\tau}_1, \hat{\eta}(s + i_1)) \geq T_{IL}(\hat{\tau}_2, T_{IL}(C_{IL}(\hat{\tau}_1, \hat{\eta}(s)), C_{IL}(\hat{\tau}_1, \hat{\eta}(i_1))))$
 $\geq T_{IL}(\hat{\tau}_2, T_{IL}(C_{IL}(\hat{\tau}_1, \hat{\eta}(s)), \hat{t}))$.

Then by condition F1, we get $a \in \eta_{\hat{t}} + s$. Therefore $s + \eta_{\hat{t}} \subseteq \eta_{\hat{t}} + s$, $\forall s \in S$.

For $s_1, s_2 \in S$, consider $s_1 \equiv_{\eta_{\hat{t}}} s_2$. This implies there exist $i_1, i_2 \in \eta_{\hat{t}}$ such that $i_1 + s_1 = i_2 + s_2$.

Then $C_{IL}(\hat{\tau}_1, \hat{\eta}(s_1)) \geq T_{IL}(\hat{\tau}_2, T_{IL}(C_{IL}(\hat{\tau}_1, \hat{\eta}(i_2 + s_2)), C_{IL}(\hat{\tau}_1, \hat{\eta}(i_1))))$
 $\geq T_{IL}(\hat{\tau}_2, T_{IL}(C_{IL}(\hat{\tau}_1, \hat{\eta}(i_2 + s_2)), \hat{t}))$.

This implies $s_1 \in \eta_{\hat{t}} + i_2 + s_2 \subseteq \eta_{\hat{t}} + s_2$.

Now, take $x \in s_1(\eta_{\hat{t}} + s_2)$. Then there exists $k_1 \in \eta_{\hat{t}}$ such that $x = s_1(k_1 + s_2)$.

Then $C_{IL}(\hat{\tau}_1, s_1(k_1 + s_2)) \geq T_{IL}(\hat{\tau}_2, T_{IL}(C_{IL}(\hat{\tau}_1, \hat{\eta}(k_1)), C_{IL}(\hat{\tau}_1, \hat{\eta}(s_1 s_2))))$
 $\geq T_{IL}(\hat{\tau}_2, T_{IL}(\hat{t}, C_{IL}(\hat{\tau}_1, \hat{\eta}(s_1 s_2))))$.

This implies $x \in \eta_{\hat{t}} + s_1 s_2$.

Let $x \in \eta_{\hat{t}} s$. Then there exists $i \in \eta_{\hat{t}}$ such that $x = is$. Then $C_{IL}(\hat{\tau}_1, \hat{\eta}(is)) \geq T_{IL}(\hat{\tau}_2, C_{IL}(\hat{\tau}_1, \hat{\eta}(i))) \geq T_{IL}(\hat{\tau}_2, C_{IL}(\hat{\tau}_1, \hat{t})) \geq T_{IL}(\hat{\tau}_2, \hat{\tau}_2) = \hat{\tau}_2$. Thus $\eta_{\hat{t}}$, $\forall \hat{t} \in [\hat{\tau}_1, \hat{\tau}_2]$ is a strong ideal of seminearring S .

□

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